

**Structural Health
Monitoring under
Uncertainty and Material
Degradation: A Review of
Fiber-Optic Sensing and
Machine Learning-Aided
Analysis**

1.Introduction

Modern large-scale civil engineering projects, including bridges, tunnels, and other essential infrastructures, play a crucial role in public life and national development. These structures not only involve considerable financial investment throughout their construction and maintenance but are also directly connected with human safety. Their expected service duration commonly extends over several decades or even centuries (Leung, 2015). Throughout this long operational period, they are inevitably subjected to environmental influences and repetitive loading, which may result in fatigue and gradual deterioration (Goyal, 2016; Supplasri, 2013). Consequently, damage in various forms and degrees accumulates within the structure, potentially causing severe accidents or economic losses. Ensuring the long-term safety and durability of such systems has therefore become a central issue in structural engineering. Real-time health monitoring and systematic evaluation are essential to identify potential weaknesses at an early stage and to improve the overall safety performance of civil facilities.

Real-time Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) offers an effective approach for detecting progressive damage, evaluating structural functionality, and estimating remaining service life. It also enables the establishment of early warning systems and supports preventive measures against possible failures or disasters (Di Sante, 2015; Rodríguez, 2015).

The SHM framework allows continuous observation of the structural “health state” by employing distributed or surface-bonded sensors that function analogously to a biological nervous system. These sensors can capture internal defects and response variations related to deformation, corrosion, and stiffness loss. In emergency or hazardous conditions, appropriate feedback and control actions can restore the structural system to a stable or optimal state. Furthermore, adaptive systems are able to preserve stability by autonomously adjusting configuration, stiffness, damping, or strength according to external stimuli (López Higuera, 2011; Diamanti, 2010). With the increasing integration of advanced sensing and numerical modeling, machine learning has emerged as a valuable complement to traditional analytical mechanics. It establishes surrogate mappings that represent the complex relationships among loads, damage indicators, and structural responses. Gaussian process modeling, in particular, provides both predictions and uncertainty bounds, offering a probabilistic foundation for active sensing, reliability evaluation, and decision optimization under uncertain conditions (Shahriari et al., 2016). In the field of structural reliability, adaptive learning techniques can refine model accuracy near the limit state by prioritizing simulations that yield the highest information gain, which significantly improves the capacity of surrogate models to discriminate critical behaviors (Echard et al., 2011).

The same surrogate modeling mechanism is also applicable to inverse problems: measured strains or displacements can be probabilistically mapped back to material parameters and damage states. Recent research on geometric and topological uncertainties has demonstrated the feasibility and effectiveness of this approach in civil systems (Wang et al., 2025). At the engineering practice level, surrogate models are often coupled with heuristic optimization to efficiently explore large design spaces; in addition, importance sampling based on metamodels can significantly accelerate the calculation of failure probabilities for rare events while maintaining unbiased estimation (Dubourg et al., 2013). In summary, relying on this closed-loop framework, real-time state assessment of civil infrastructure and cost-constrained decision support can be achieved.

2. Structural Uncertainty and Material Degradation

2.1 Structural Uncertainty

Uncertainty is an inherent characteristic of structural properties, which may arise from various sources such as materials, measurements, manufacturing, processing, and environment. Therefore, the true state (such as stiffness, damage, and load-bearing capacity reserve) cannot be directly observed and must be indirectly inferred and quantified through the integration of sensor data within the framework of uncertainty quantification, virtual modeling, and Bayesian learning; these results are then used for reliability and lifespan assessment as well as decision-making (Wang et al., 2024a, 2024b).

Traditionally, uncertainty is divided into aleatory uncertainty and epistemic uncertainty. Aleatory uncertainty refers to unknown factors that may vary each time the same experiment is conducted. Assuming complete information to determine the relevant probability density function (PDF), it can be modeled through probabilistic methods. On the other hand, epistemic uncertainty is characterized by incompleteness and imprecision, which may be caused by insufficient knowledge, inaccurate measurements, rounding errors, noise in experimental data, and imperfect theoretical models used to describe the real process. There are various methods available for modeling epistemic uncertainty, including possibility theory, fuzzy set theory, evidence theory, and probabilistic theory under Bayesian interpretation.

2.1.1 Geometric and Connection Uncertainties

Extensive studies have demonstrated that the presence of initial bending, twisting, and residual stresses greatly increases the sensitivity of the buckling–yield interaction, thereby exerting a major influence on both the strength and ductility evaluation of structural members. To describe these imperfections within a consistent numerical framework, the concept of equivalent geometric imperfections (EGI) has been broadly applied in geometric and material nonlinear analysis (GMNIA). Quan et al. (2024) established GMNIA-based recommendations for the definition of imperfections and design guidance for steel as well as stainless-steel beam–columns. Building upon this, Gardner et al. (2022) extended the EGI methodology to address out-of-plane stability and proposed practical specifications for the magnitude and configuration of imperfections in GNIA and GMNIA analyses. Collectively, the EGI combined with the GMNIA framework provides a unified path for the consideration of imperfections in nonlinear simulations. Nevertheless, further improvement is still required in establishing the statistical foundations for imperfection amplitudes, accounting for variations among material types, and systematically quantifying member-scale effects.

2.1.2 Load Uncertainties

Load uncertainty is reflected in the randomness, temporal variability, and statistical interdependence of external actions. Four principal sources are commonly distinguished: dead load, live load, environmental load, and extreme events, with the last category marked by very small probability but very large consequence (Ellingwood, 1982). Dead loads arise mainly from construction tolerances and material variability, and are typically represented with a small coefficient of variation using a normal distribution to capture systematic bias (Nowak, 2013). Live loads depend on occupancy and operational patterns, display stronger temporal correlation, and are often described by lognormal laws for long term averages, while short term maxima are better

fitted by extreme value families. As monitoring becomes widespread, measured data can be brought into a Bayesian updating scheme to revise load parameters in real time and enable adaptive reliability assessment (Zhang, 2023).

For wind actions, directionality and multivariate dependence are central considerations. Unified extreme wind formulations treat multidirectional wind speeds as a joint random field and use multivariate extreme value theory to capture directional coupling, which permits a joint evaluation with structural response (Chen, 2015). Seismic load uncertainty is driven by the stochastic nature of ground motion fields together with site amplification effects. Representative records can be produced through spectral matching and randomized procedures to quantify the dispersion in time history responses (Der Kiureghian, 1977). When confronting unconventional hazards such as bushfires, wave impacts, or explosions, data scarcity and spatial temporal heterogeneity motivate the use of virtual simulations and surrogate models to reconstruct load distributions and to conduct vulnerability and reliability studies (Shi, 2024). In parallel, the rising frequency of climate related extremes has encouraged nonstationary stochastic descriptions to reflect long term environmental trends and their implications for structural safety (Forzieri, 2022). Taken together, research on load uncertainty is moving away from purely classical sampling toward integrated, data informed, and physically consistent modeling. A Bayesian updating framework that fuses monitoring evidence, empirical distributions, and mechanistic models yields a continuously refreshed prediction of load effects and offers more robust support for life cycle design and resilience assessment (Wang, 2024b).

2.1.3 Environmental and Operational Variability (EOV)

EOV represents the slow drift and periodic fluctuations over time in temperature, humidity, wind field, sunlight, as well as operating conditions and operational rhythms. These exogenous drivers can induce coordinated changes in frequency, damping, modal shape, strain, and electrochemical signals, thereby obscuring subtle damage characteristics and increasing the risk of false alarms. Empirical studies have shown that even if the structure is not damaged, environmental effects can cause natural frequency shifts of several percentage points, which are sufficient to perturb threshold-based diagnostics and distance-metric-based indicators (Reynders, 2012; Worden, 2007). A more robust approach in engineering is to establish an environmental-response baseline first. By using environmental variables as explanatory variables and eliminating common trends through regression, principal component analysis, and cointegration techniques, the residual signal becomes more sensitive to damage. Subsequently, the diagnosis and reliability assessment processes can be initiated (Staszewski, 2023). At the model level, support vector regression and Gaussian processes can characterize nonlinear covariant relationships and be combined with Bayesian filtering to update environmental states and uncertainties online, enabling simultaneous performance evaluation and data assimilation (Svensson, 2023).

2.1.4 Model-Form Uncertainty

Model form uncertainty is the systematic deviation between theoretical model, numerical approximation and real structural behavior. Even if the parameters are recalibrated, the model may still be inconsistent with the measured results due to idealized assumptions, simplified boundary conditions or scale effects (Kennedy, 2001). If this difference is not explicitly handled, it is often

"mistakenly absorbed" as a parameter adjustment, resulting in parameter compensation error, resulting in too narrow prediction interval, wrong damage judgment or high reliability evaluation. In order to quantify the deviation of the model from reality, researchers usually model the model error as a random process or additional noise term, and update it with the observation data under the hierarchical Bayesian framework (Malek, 2021). This can express the uncertainty at the parameter and model levels at the same time, so as to avoid mixing systematic errors with material or geometric parameters. Another method is to improve the robustness and confidence interval reliability of prediction by fusing the balance deviation and variance of multiple models (Zhang, 2024).

2.2 Mechanisms and Manifestations of Material Degradation

Material degradation is the physical and chemical expression of uncertainty's evolution under long-term service conditions, manifesting as irreversible deterioration of mechanical and durability properties as structures interact with their environment.

2.2.1 Physical Degradation

Physical degradation arises from repeated environmental actions such as temperature gradients, humidity fluctuations, and mechanical wear. In concrete, cycles of freezing and thawing drive moisture migration and ice formation in capillary pores, producing hydraulic pressure that initiates microcracks and progressively lowers stiffness; the rate of damage growth depends on saturation, pore structure, and the severity and number of cycles, and can be exacerbated by deicing salts through surface scaling and spalling (Powers and Helmuth, 1953). In metallic components and composite systems, thermal fatigue caused by recurring temperature swings induces local strain incompatibilities and microstructural damage, while prolonged ultraviolet exposure leads to photo-oxidation, coating chalking, and microcracking of surface films; the resulting loss of barrier integrity increases susceptibility to subsequent chemical attack and abrasion, accelerating section loss or delamination under service loading (Leung et al., 2015). From a monitoring perspective, these processes manifest as gradual shifts in dynamic modulus, resonance frequency, damping, and wave velocity, which can be captured by strain, vibration, and fiber-optic measurements to support timely maintenance and life cycle reliability assessment (Leung et al., 2015).

2.2.2 Chemical Degradation

Chemical degradation arises from interactions between structural materials and aggressive media and progresses through transport, reaction, and damage accumulation. In cementitious systems, carbonation proceeds as carbon dioxide diffuses into the pore network and reacts with portlandite to form calcium carbonate, which lowers the pore solution pH and removes the passive condition of embedded steel; once passivity is lost, corrosion initiation becomes possible even under moderate moisture exposure (Bertolini et al., 2013). Chloride ingress is governed largely by Fickian diffusion and capillary suction, with thresholds at the steel surface controlling pit nucleation; subsequent propagation depends on oxygen availability, moisture cycles, and electrical resistivity, which together favour localized attack in the form of pitting and crevice corrosion (Liu and Weyers, 1998; Bertolini et al., 2013).

For metallic members, the corrosion rate is strongly conditioned by the exposure class and

electrochemical state, including wet–dry cycling, salinity, temperature, and the prevailing potential; mechanistic regimes range from oxygen controlled dissolution to diffusion limited processes, and these regimes can evolve over time as rust layers develop and environmental conditions change (Melchers, 2003). In polymer matrix composites, moisture uptake and elevated temperature promote hydrolysis and oxidation, which plasticize and embrittle the matrix, reduce the glass transition temperature, and weaken the fibre–matrix interphase; the resulting interfacial debonding degrades load transfer efficiency and encourages microcracking and delamination under service loading (Di Sante, 2015). Overall, these chemical pathways often interact with physical transport and mechanical cycling, so reliable assessment requires coupled models that reflect both environmental exposure and material specific reaction kinetics.

2.2.3 Mechanical Degradation

Mechanical degradation develops under fatigue, creep, and repeated loading. In metallic members, damage typically initiates at microstructural slip bands, proceeds to small crack formation, and then enters a long crack growth regime that can be described by the Paris relation, where the growth rate depends on the stress intensity range as well as stress ratio, mean stress, environment, and residual stresses. Near the threshold and close to fracture toughness, departures from the Paris regime become important for life prediction, and the distinction between low cycle and high cycle conditions further shapes the evolution of damage (Schijve, 2009).

Concrete and masonry exhibit time dependent deformation under sustained actions, combining viscoelastic creep with microcracking. The rate and magnitude of creep are influenced by stress level, age at loading, temperature, and moisture state, while shrinkage arises from drying and autogenous processes and alters internal stress, stiffness, and deflection over service life. Together these mechanisms reduce effective modulus and can modify crack opening and closure under variable actions (Bazant, 1999).

In multi phase or layered systems such as laminated composites or fiber reinforced strengthening schemes, mismatch in stiffness and thermal expansion generates interfacial shear and peel stresses. Cyclic mechanical and environmental loading promotes interfacial debonding and delamination, which in turn accelerates fatigue and creep, diminishes load transfer, and shifts dynamic characteristics such as natural frequency and damping (Cao et al., 2019).

2.2.4 Coupled and Stochastic Degradation

In practice, degradation processes seldom act alone. The combined action of corrosion and fatigue, the joint effect of chloride ingress with freeze and thaw cycles, and the synergy between thermal exposure and chemical attack generate nonlinear responses with memory, so damage accumulation depends on the loading history, temperature and moisture paths, and even prior repairs; this increases dispersion in time dependent reliability estimates (Stewart and Rosowsky, 1998). Contemporary probabilistic descriptions therefore use stochastic processes at the component or field level. Gamma processes capture monotonic capacity loss, while diffusion type models represent transport controlled deterioration, with parameters allowed to vary in space to reflect exposure conditions and material heterogeneity. These formulations are often embedded in hierarchical Bayesian schemes and linked to monitoring data through state space inference. To control computational cost, data informed surrogates such as Gaussian process emulators and SOCP-X-SVR models are trained on high fidelity simulations and then used for sequential

updating, sensitivity analysis, and posterior prediction under mixed aleatory and epistemic uncertainty (Oumouni et al., 2019; Gao et al., 2023).

2.3 Effects of Degradation on Structural Performance

Degradation progressively modifies resistance, stiffness, and energy dissipation capacity, which diminishes ultimate strength, reduces service performance, and raises vulnerability to adverse actions. In metallic systems, corrosion induced loss of cross section redistributes mass and stiffness, shifting natural frequencies, altering mode shapes, and changing damping, effects that complicate modal identification, damage localization, and model updating (Rodrigues et al., 2021). From a probabilistic viewpoint, deterioration turns nominal design parameters into time dependent random processes, so the reliability index $\beta(t)$ evolves under the joint influence of degradation kinetics and the propagation of uncertainty through models, loads, and measurements (Li et al., 2020).

Within life cycle assessment, deterioration models are coupled with resilience based formulations in which performance loss, recovery trajectories, and adaptive interventions are treated as interconnected stochastic processes and evaluated over time with consistent decision metrics (Yang and Frangopol, 2019). In parallel, the fusion of optical and distributed sensing with surrogate learning, for example SOCP-X-SVR, supports inverse identification of latent material and damage parameters, continuous updating of remaining useful life, and near real time prognosis from monitoring streams, thereby enabling risk informed inspection planning and maintenance prioritization (López Higuera et al., 2011; Gao et al., 2023).

3.Sensor

In the process of structural health monitoring, the system collects dynamic response measurement data through sensors. Characteristic factors sensitive to damage are extracted from these measurement data, and statistical analysis is performed on these characteristic factors to obtain the current health status of the structure. To achieve comprehensive monitoring of strain, displacement, temperature, vibration, etc. of large structures, hundreds of sensors are usually required (Linderma, 2013;Rice,2010). Common sensors used in structural health monitoring systems include piezoelectric elements (Qing,2006; Liu,2007;Zou,2013), strain elements (Li,2013;Xiandong, 2013), and fiber optic sensors (FOS) (Leung,2015; Barria,2016; Ye,2014). Piezoelectric elements have advantages such as high sensitivity, good dynamic performance, and wide application range, but they also have disadvantages such as high brittleness, difficulty in embedding into structures, and low-frequency characteristics. Strain elements have characteristics of high sensitivity, good static performance, and stable performance. However, traditional resistance strain gauge monitoring systems are difficult to meet the needs of practical engineering structural health monitoring in terms of performance stability, durability, and distribution range. In recent years, with the development of material and structural damage signal processing technology and the continuous progress of sensing technology, fiber optic sensors have successfully entered our field of vision. Fiber optic sensors have advantages such as small size, light weight, corrosion resistance, electromagnetic interference resistance, and ease of embedding, and have been rapidly developed and applied internationally (Barrias,2016; Ye,2014).

3.1 Classification and Principles of Fiber-Optic Sensor (FOS)

The work of optical fiber sensor includes the monitoring of external factors and signal transmission. When the light propagates in the optical fiber, the intensity, phase, polarization state, frequency and other characteristic parameters of the light will change. Therefore, FOS can be divided into intensity modulated FOS, phase modulated FOS, polarization modulated Fos and frequency modulated FOS. In Fos system, when the light in the optical fiber is transmitted from the light source to the detector, the modulation occurs inside the optical fiber, which is called intrinsic FOS. The modulation outside the fiber is called extrinsic FOS. In addition, FOS is divided into interference Fos and non-interference FOS according to the interference of light. According to the sensing range, FOS can be divided into point (local) FOS, quasi distributed Fos and distributed FOS. Fabry Perot optical fiber sensors (fpfos) are most commonly used in civil infrastructure (Guo,2012; Zhang,2013), fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors (kinet,2014; Leung,2015; ; Chachapová,2019) and long period fiber Bragg grating (LPFG) sensor (Zhang,2013).

3.1.1 Fabry Perot optical fiber sensor

The optical fiber sensor uses the optical phase change under the influence of physical field to reflect the characteristics of the measured object. After the light source is emitted, the light is divided into two beams with the same frequency, polarization direction and initial phase through the prism. One beam is signal light and the other is reference light. They interfere when they meet. The interference image can be used to infer the influence of external factors on the signal light.

Fig.3.1 Structure diagrams of a typical (a) IFPI, (b) EFPI and (c) ILFPI

The core of FPFOS is interference cavity. According to the different structure of interference cavity, FPFOS can be divided into intrinsic type and extrinsic type (Fig.3.2). In the intrinsic Fabry Perot interference (IFPI) sensing system, the interference cavity is usually composed of a single-mode fiber and an insulating mirror, and the end face cut by the fiber can be used as a mirror (Wang,2010; Zhang,2013). In the extrinsic Fabry Perot interference (EFPI) sensing system, the interference cavity is composed of air or other non fiber solid media (Guo,2012; Gao,2018). The above two types use the physical parameters to be measured to cause the change of phase difference, so that the optical path difference changes, and then convert the interference signal into electrical signal for processing through the monitor.

Fig.3.2 Functional principle of EFPI (Leung,2015)

3.1.2 Fiber Bragg Grating Sensor

SHM is the most widely used field of FBG sensors (Leung,2015; kinet,2014). Low manufacturing cost, high-quality demodulation system and practical packaging technology are important reasons for the wide application of FBG sensors (kinet,2014;Mihailov,2012;Hong,2016). FBG sensors can be attached to the structure surface or embedded in the structure to achieve real-time monitoring of the structure and monitor the formation of structural defects (Torres,2011). In addition, a large number of FBG sensors can be connected in series to form a sensor network system, and the sensing signal can be remotely accessed to the central monitoring room for subsequent data analysis and processing (Wang,2015). At present, FBG sensor has become a common sensor in the field of grating sensing (Mihailov,2012). The structure and principle of FBG are shown in Figure 3.3 and Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.3 The principles and wavelength shift of fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors.(Niharika, N,2014)

Fig.3.4 Working principle of fiber Bragg grating (Wan,2015)

Quasi distributed fiber optic gyroscope based on Fiber Bragg grating is one of the most important fiber Bragg grating sensors. The quasi distributed fiber Bragg grating sensor uses signal transmission fiber to connect multiple fibers or sensors together and separate the optical signals of different sensors, so as to analyze the monitoring data collected by different sensors. Compared with vibrating wire sensor and resistance sensor, it does not need to set transmission optical fiber separately at each monitoring point, which makes engineering monitoring more convenient, lower cost and more efficient. Therefore, the quasi distributed FBG sensor is more suitable for monitoring the key parts of large structures and realizing multi parameter measurement (Johnson,2010; Marques,2015).

The wavelength signals collected by fiber Bragg grating sensors can contain temperature and strain information. In fiber Bragg grating sensing technology, how to separate the crosstalk between strain and temperature is a key problem. Many scholars have proposed many solutions for the cross sensitivity of fiber Bragg grating. These solutions can be roughly divided into: two parameter method, temperature (strain) compensation method, special performance fiber Bragg grating method, etc. In 2011, Stefani and Alessio (Stefani,2011) proposed a method of temperature compensation using adjacent grating strain sensors. In 2013, Ping Lu et al. (Harris,2013) used high-sensitivity outer layer mode to realize temperature and axial strain compensation. In 2014, Wang Yiping (2013) reduced the cross sensitivity between tensile strain and temperature by changing the length of the cavity through repeated arc discharge. Therefore, in order to solve the crosstalk between strain and temperature and distinguish strain, temperature compensation is needed.

3.1.3 Long-Period Fiber Grating (LPFG) Sensor

Long period fiber grating (LPFG) is a new type of fiber passive grating, which forms periodic or aperiodic refractive index distribution in the core. The long period of LPFG makes the resonant wavelength and amplitude very sensitive to the changes of ambient temperature, strain, bending and torsion. In addition, LPFG is a kind of transmission fiber grating with high measurement accuracy. Therefore, it is more and more widely used in optical fiber sensing (Zhang,2012; Gao,2014)

3.2 Typical Fiber-Optical Sensors

3.2.1 Crack Sensors

Optical fiber sensors used for crack detection are primarily categorized into grating sensors and distributed optical fiber sensors. These crack detection sensors are primarily employed to monitor the stability of concrete structures and find widespread applications in assessing the health and stability of bridges, buildings, and tunnels (Rodríguez,2015; Du,2019).

Fig.3.5 Schematic diagram of an OTDR based multi-gauge crack sensor (Leung, 2015)

Fig.3.6 Sensing principle of the OTDR based distributed crack sensor (Leung, 2015)

In crack monitoring, due to the heterogeneity and complexity of concrete materials, it is difficult to accurately monitor the number and depth of cracks in concrete structures. Bao (2010) proposed a distributed crack fiber optic sensor based on optical time domain reflectometry (OTDR), which achieves full coverage monitoring of all cracks without the need to determine their locations in advance. The relationship curve between backscattered power and light propagation distance sharply decreases at cracks, allowing for their identification. This sensor uses short optical pulses as the light source and measures the backscattered optical power through an OTDR (Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6). One advantage of distributed fiber optic sensing is that it can monitor all points along the fiber (Rodríguez,2015), accurately locating cracks. Based on the this, Niharika (2014) proposed a novel S-shaped fiber optic layout that improves sensitivity while maintaining the distributed characteristics of the sensing system.

3.2.2 Temperature Sensors

The temperature effect of concrete structures is closely related to their structural health (Ouyang,2019). Temperature monitoring determines the quality, thermal resistance, and cold resistance of concrete structures. Currently, a relatively mature technology is the use of distributed fiber optic temperature sensing. It can achieve testing of thousands of data points through a single sensor.

In the early days, Rao (1997) proposed a fiber optic Fabry–Perot sensor based on wavelength multiplexing, which can simultaneously measure static strain, temperature, and vibration in structural health monitoring (SHM). It can be installed on the surface or embedded inside the structure to achieve distributed temperature sensing monitoring. Zou (2012) designed a Fabry–Perot fiber optic temperature sensor to study temperature changes during the hydration process of concrete, and derived a temperature curve (as shown in Figure 3.7), which is used to calculate the apparent activation energy and hydration heat of concrete. These parameters can be used to predict the future structural health status.

Figure 3.7 Concrete hydration experiment with water versus cement ratio 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6 using the thermocouple (Zou,2012).

3.2.3 Strain Sensors

In the process of Structural Health Monitoring (SHM), the degree of deformation of a structure can be identified using density information. Therefore, identifying the stress or damage imposed on the structure is crucial for ensuring its health. In recent years, fiber optic sensors have been widely used to measure the internal strain of structures (Figure 3.8).

Sridevi (2016) reported an etched fiber Bragg grating (eFBG) sensor coated with reduced graphene oxide (rGO), which significantly enhanced the sensitivity to strain and temperature. However, the most commonly used FBG sensors and distributed fiber optic sensors (DFOS) are unable to provide multi-parameter sensing. Drissi-Habti (2017) proposed a method for positioning using a sine wave sensor. Linearly arranged FOS can only detect transverse strain, while sine wave-arranged FOS can provide information on linear, shear, and transverse strain (Figure 3.9). When FOS is embedded in large structures, it is difficult to identify multi-axial strain. If the direction of the applied strain is random, linearly arranged FOS cannot distinguish strain

coordinates. Therefore, in composite materials, using distributed FOS sine wave alignment for multi-axial strain is the optimal solution.

Figure 3.8 Fiber-optic sensor installation method for a reference surface area (Drissi-Ha,2017)

Figure 3.9 Schematic diagram of a FBG strain sensor with self temperature compensation (Leung, 2015)

In recent years, femtosecond (FS) lasers have garnered significant attention due to their extremely high peak power, high spatial resolution, and ultrashort duration. FS lasers offer the advantage of reducing the cavity length of fiber Bragg gratings (FBGs), further minimizing cross-sensitivity to temperature. Additionally, the thickness of the diaphragm can be controlled to meet specific requirements for pressure sensitivity and measurement range. Introducing FS lasers into gratings has become a trend (Islam,2014). Yinan Zhang (2013) proposed a femtosecond laser micro-machining method for fabricating diaphragm-based FPI sensors for pressure measurement at high temperatures.

Table 1 compares the reported performance of EFPI-type optical fiber sensors between 2005 and 2020. The parameters include temperature-measurement range and sensitivity, as well as strain or pressure measurement range and corresponding sensitivity. Results show that later designs have progressively widened both measurement ranges and sensitivities through improved cavity materials and optical demodulation schemes (OPD), achieving sub-picometer resolution and broad applicability from cryogenic (-50°C) to ultra-high-temperature (1600°C) environments.

Table 1 Comparison of parameters of various EFPIs (Li, A.,2022)

EFPI	Temperature Measurement Range	Temperature Sensitivity	Strain/Pressure Measurement Range	Strain/Pressure Sensitivity
2005	230-1600 °C	2.798 nm/°C		
2010	20-1050 °C	20 pm/°C(OPD)		
2012	100-700 °C	0.98 pm/°C	0~800 $\mu\epsilon$	3.14 pm/ $\mu\epsilon$
2013	200-700 °C	4.44 pm/°C	0~689.5 kPa	0.28 pm/Pa
2014	20-800 °C	0.59 pm/°C	0~3700 $\mu\epsilon$	1.5 pm/ $\mu\epsilon$
2017	23~600 °C	12.3 pm/°C	0~2104 $\mu\epsilon$	1.74 pm/ $\mu\epsilon$
2017	23~600 °C	0.51 pm/°C	0~3 MPa	1.53 nm/MPa(600 °C)
2017	23~1000 °C	20.31 pm/°C		
2018	20~600 °C	0.17 pm/°C	0~1.0 MPa	-5.912 nm/MPa(600 °C)
2018	20~800 °C	14.8 pm/°C	0.1~0.7 MPa	4.28 nm/MPa
2018	0~800 °C	19.8 nm/°C(OPD)	0~10 MPa	98 nm/MPa
2019	100~1080 °C	4.786 nm/°C(OPD)		
2019	20~1000 °C	12.26 nm/°C		
2019	20~1000 °C	108.11 pm/°C(OPD)	0~10 MPa	70.85 nm/MPa
2019	20~1000 °C	15.41 pm/°C	0~1000 $\mu\epsilon$	1.19 pm/ $\mu\epsilon$ (900 °C)
2020	25~1000 °C	0.77 pm/°C		
2020	-50~1200 °C	23 pm/°C	0.4~4.0 MPa	1.2 nm/MPa(1200 °C)
2020	23~1455 °C	1.32 nm/°C(OPD)		
2020	100~1000 °C	18.01 pm/°C	0~450 $\mu\epsilon$	2.17 pm/ $\mu\epsilon$ (800 °C)

3.3 Applications of Fiber-Optic Sensor

3.3.1 Bridges

Currently, due to the limitations in understanding complex bridge structures and the impacts of factors such as extended service life, corrosion, fatigue, earthquakes, and floods, accurate prediction and control become challenging. To ensure the safety and durability of large bridges, it

is essential to monitor their structural health in real-time, thereby ensuring safe and normal operation and extending their lifespan. Ye Xiaowei (2018) proposed a stress monitoring scheme for orthotropic steel bridges using fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensing technology. In this work, FBG sensors were deployed at the mid-span and quarter-span locations of the bridge, specifically on the rib plates and deck slabs prone to fatigue, as well as on the welded joints between the rib plates and crossbeams, as illustrated in Figure 3.10.

Figure 3.10 Deployment of structural health monitoring (SHM) system based on fiber Bragg grating (FBG) (Li, Y,2016)

3.3.2 Buildings

To better understand the complex behaviors of modern buildings and structures, computational methods such as finite element modeling are often employed during the design phase. However, even complex computer models involve numerous assumptions and uncertainties. Taking the Guangzhou New TV Tower (**Figure 3.11**) as an example, it is a tube-in-tube structure with a height of 610 meters. Its structural behavior is extremely complex, especially the interaction between wind and the structure. It is even impossible to reliably collect and obtain wind characteristics at the top of the building. As shown in Figure 13, 120 fiber Bragg grating (FBG) strain and temperature sensors were installed at five different height levels of the Guangzhou New TV Tower for monitoring during operation (Ni,2009). The FBG strain sensors were welded onto the surface of the outer tube column structural steel to measure cumulative strain and dynamic strain.

Figure 3.11 Schematic diagram of the sensor allocations in Guangzhou New TV Tower (Leung, 2015)

4. Machine Learning Aided Structural Analysis and Optimization

4.1 Surrogate Model

Surrogate models in structural engineering are simplified mathematical or machine learning representations that stand in for expensive finite element simulations. They approximate the input response mapping of complex models closely enough to support design studies, optimisation, and reliability evaluation without repeatedly running full analyses. In this sense, a surrogate functions as an efficient emulator, preserving the essential physics that drive the response while substantially reducing computational cost.

Common families of surrogates include polynomial response surfaces, Gaussian process regression also known as Kriging, support vector regression, and deep neural networks. Kriging is often preferred when uncertainty quantification is important because it delivers a mean prediction together with a measure of predictive spread. Support vector regression and neural models handle strong nonlinearity and high dimensional inputs effectively. Physics informed neural networks further embed equilibrium relations and constitutive laws into the training objective so that the learned model respects basic mechanics and extrapolates more reliably when only a modest amount of data is available.

In practice, surrogates are frequently coupled with active learning. The model is used to identify regions near limit states or design frontiers where additional simulations would be most informative, and new samples are added to refine accuracy with the fewest extra runs. Recent workflows also employ Bayesian optimisation to search design spaces and reinforcement learning to steer topology optimisation or parameter calibration in complex systems. Taken together, these strategies create a bridge between high fidelity simulation and decision making by enabling fast prediction, explicit uncertainty quantification, sensitivity screening, and data driven exploration across the life cycle of modern civil and structural engineering problems.

4.2 Several types of Surrogate Models used in this research

4.2.1 Gaussian process regression (GPR) inverse surrogate workflow

Gaussian process expression in this topic is used to make a reverse proxy model, which maps the response characteristics calculated by the finite element method back to the material parameters. This idea can be seen as an extension of Kriging's agent and computer experiment design idea, which has been put forward in the work of sacks et al. (sacks et al., 1989), and Rasmussen and Williams made a systematic summary of Gaussian process regression (2006).

1. Basic settings and symbols

Considering the finite element model of cantilever beam, the material parameters are written as a two-dimensional vector $\theta = \begin{pmatrix} E \\ \nu \end{pmatrix}$, Where E is the equivalent modulus of elasticity and ν Poisson's ratio. Under given conditions θ , the displacement field or stress field along a certain sampling line will be obtained by finite element analysis. In order to reduce the dimension, the whole curve is compressed into a feature vector, and the classical method of principal component analysis is more convenient (Jolliffe, 2002). Note that the eigenvector is $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^p$, p is the selected characteristic dimension. We want to have a function from the characteristic space to the material parameter space: $\theta = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{pmatrix} E(\mathbf{x}) \\ \nu(\mathbf{x}) \end{pmatrix}$. In this way, if there is a new feature \mathbf{x} , possibly from the

monitoring data collected by sensors, the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the material can be deduced by the surrogate model, so as to carry out the subsequent structural health monitoring

2. limited metadata and training samples

Firstly, the reasonable range of material parameters is given, which can be directly written in the form of inequality without interval symbol $E_{min} \leq E \leq E_{max}, \nu_{min} \leq \nu \leq \nu_{max}$. Within this parameter range, Latin hypercube sampling is used for sample design, which is a common uniform sampling method in computer experiments (sacks et al., 1989; Santner et al., 2018).

Get N groups of material parameters $\theta_i = \begin{pmatrix} E_i \\ \nu_i \end{pmatrix}, i = 1, \dots, N$. Each group of θ is sent into COMSOL model, and the response curve along the sampling line is derived after recalculation and solution. Perform principal component analysis on the responses of all samples, and take the first p principal components as the eigenvector of the sample, meeting the $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^p$. Finally, all feature vectors are stacked into a feature matrix X , and the corresponding E and ν form an output matrix Y , which is saved in the *features.mat* file of MATLAB for subsequent training.

3. Gaussian process prior

Specify a Gaussian process to validate the model first. For any output component q (which can be E or ν), assume that there is a formula: $q(x) \sim \mathcal{GP}(m_q(x), k_q(x, x'))$. Where $q(x)$ is the mean function, usually set to 0. $k_q(x, x')$ is the covariance kernel function, which is used to describe the correlation structure between different features. The commonly used square exponential kernel and Matérn kernel are discussed in detail in Rasmussen and Williams' book (2006). The kernel function encompasses a set of hyperparameters, including signal variance, length scales in each direction, and noise variance, which are denoted as a vector ϕ_q .

4. Covariance matrix and log marginal likelihood

Record the output of the i th sample in the training set as q_i , and all outputs form a column vector: $y_q = \begin{pmatrix} q_1 \\ \vdots \\ q_N \end{pmatrix}$. Given the hyper parameter ϕ_q .

The covariance matrix between the training samples is written as

$$K\phi_q(i, j) = k_q(x_i, x_j; \phi_q) + \sigma_{n,q}^2 \delta_{ij}.$$

$\sigma_{n,q}^2$ denotes the noise variance and δ_{ij} is the Kronecker symbol.

The hyperparameters are learned by maximising the log marginal likelihood of the observations, which is the usual choice in Gaussian process regression (Rasmussen and Williams, 2006).

For the output vector, the log marginal likelihood is

$$\log p(y_q | \mathcal{X}, \phi_q) = -\frac{1}{2} y_q^\top K_{\phi_q}^{-1} y_q - \frac{1}{2} \log |K_{\phi_q}| - \frac{1}{2} N \log(2\pi)$$

In numerical implementation, an initial guess of ϕ_q is chosen, then K_{ϕ_q} is built and factorised by a Cholesky decomposition. The log marginal likelihood and its gradient are evaluated, and a gradient-based or quasi-Newton algorithm updates the hyperparameters until convergence. In the present work, these steps are wrapped inside MATLAB routines such as GPRpredictENu, which read the matrices X and Y , train one model for E and one for ν , and store the resulting hyperparameters.

5. Prediction and parameter inversion

After the training, the new eigenvector \mathbf{x}_* can be predicted. First give the covariance vector

between it and the training sample: $\mathbf{k}_q^* = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{k}_q(\mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{x}_1) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{k}_q(\mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{x}_N) \end{pmatrix}$, and the covariance of the new point

$\mathbf{k}_q(\mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{x}_*; \boldsymbol{\phi}_q)$. Given a data-set \mathbf{D} , the posterior predictive distribution of GPR for \mathbf{q}_* follows a one-dimensional normal distribution: $\mathbf{q}_* | \mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{D} \sim N(\boldsymbol{\mu}_q(\mathbf{x}_*), \boldsymbol{\sigma}_q^2(\mathbf{x}_*))$. The predicted mean value is

$\boldsymbol{\mu}_q(\mathbf{x}_*) = \mathbf{k}_{q,*}^\top \mathbf{K}_{\phi_q}^{-1} \mathbf{y}_q$, and forecast variance is $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_q^2(\mathbf{x}_*) = \mathbf{k}_q(\mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{x}_*; \boldsymbol{\phi}_q) - \mathbf{k}_{q,*}^\top \mathbf{K}_{\phi_q}^{-1} \mathbf{k}_{q,*}$. This set of

mean and variance formulas is the core closed form solution of GPR. Many reliability and active learning methods are constructed based on these two expressions (Rasmussen and Williams, 2006; Bichon et al., 2008; ECHARD et al., 2011).

4.2.2 K-fold cross-validation of the Gaussian process surrogate

The Gaussian process regression surrogate in Section 4.1.1 is evaluated by a K-fold cross-validation scheme. The main purpose is to check how stable the inverse mapping remains when parts of the dataset are temporarily removed, and to obtain error measures that are less optimistic than a simple fit on the full sample. K-fold cross-validation is a standard tool in statistical learning (Hastie et al., 2009), and it is convenient in this context because the training of one Gaussian process model is still relatively inexpensive compared with a finite element analysis. In the present work, the feature matrix \mathbf{X} and the corresponding outputs $\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{E}, \boldsymbol{\nu}]$ are randomly partitioned into \mathbf{K} disjoint folds of approximately equal size. One fold is taken as a validation set and the remaining $\mathbf{K}-1$ folds form the training set. For fold j , the training data are denoted by $(\mathbf{X}_{train}^{(j)}, \mathbf{Y}_{train}^{(j)})$, and the validation data are denoted by $(\mathbf{X}_{val}^{(j)}, \mathbf{Y}_{val}^{(j)})$. The Gaussian process regression model is fitted on the training part, using the marginal likelihood based hyperparameter training described in Section 4.1.1 and in Rasmussen and Williams (2006), and then it is used to predict the outputs on the validation part. This procedure is repeated over all folds so that each observation is used exactly once for validation and several times for training. In the implementation of this thesis, the K-fold cross-validation follows the steps below.

1. The number of folds \mathbf{K} is fixed in advance. In the numerical examples $\mathbf{K}=5$ is used as a compromise between computational time and robustness of the error estimate. The indices $\{\mathbf{1}, \dots, \mathbf{N}\}$ of all samples are randomly shuffled.

2. The shuffled indices are split into \mathbf{K} disjoint subsets $\mathbf{I}_1, \dots, \mathbf{I}_\mathbf{K}$ of approximately equal size. Each subset becomes one validation fold.

3. For each fold $j = \mathbf{1}, \dots, \mathbf{K}$, the training and validation sets are defined by $\mathbf{X}_{train}^{(j)} =$

$\mathbf{X}(\{\mathbf{1}, \dots, \mathbf{N}\} \setminus \mathbf{I}_j, :)$, $\mathbf{X}_{val}^{(j)} = \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{I}_j, :)$. And similarly, $\mathbf{Y}_{train}^{(j)} = \mathbf{Y}(\{\mathbf{1}, \dots, \mathbf{N}\} \setminus \mathbf{I}_j, :)$, $\mathbf{Y}_{val}^{(j)} =$

$\mathbf{Y}(\mathbf{I}_j, :)$. Two Gaussian process models are then trained on $(\mathbf{X}_{train}^{(j)}, \mathbf{Y}_{train}^{(j)})$, one for the elastic

modulus and one for the poisson ratio. For each model the kernel hyperparameters are identified

by maximising the log marginal likelihood, following the usual Gaussian process procedure (Rasmussen and Williams, 2006). The fitted models are used to predict the outputs on $\mathbf{X}_{val}^{(j)}$, and the predictions $\hat{\mathbf{E}}_i^{(j)}, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_i^{(j)}$ are stored at the corresponding indices $i \in I_j$.

4. After all folds have been processed, the predictions from each fold are assembled into global vectors $\hat{\mathbf{E}}_i$ and $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i$, which are aligned with the true values \mathbf{E}_i and \mathbf{v}_i for all $i = 1, \dots, N$.

5. Using these global prediction and target vectors, the root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE) and coefficient of determination R^2 are computed for each material parameter. For a generic scalar target y_i and its prediction \hat{y}_i , the indicators are defined as

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2},$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\hat{y}_i - y_i|,$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2},$$

Where \bar{y} is the empirical mean of the true values. These formulas are applied separately to \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{v} , and the results are reported as $RMSE_E, RMSE_v, MAE_E, MAE_v$, and the corresponding R^2 value.

6. Finally, the residuals $\hat{\mathbf{E}}_i - \mathbf{E}_i$ and $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i - \mathbf{v}_i$ are inspected in a more qualitative way, for example through histograms and scatter plots. A roughly centred and symmetric residual pattern suggests that the Gaussian process prior and the chosen kernel hyperparameters are adequate for the present feature representation. Systematic trends in the residuals, such as a bias that depends on the magnitude of the true parameter, would indicate that the kernel family or the feature extraction stage should be revised (Hastie et al., 2009).

The K-fold cross-validation results obtained through this procedure provide a reference level for the predictive capability of the Gaussian process inverse surrogate. In the next subsections, the same data are used to construct ridge regression and SOCP based support vector regression surrogates, which are then compared to the Gaussian process benchmark in terms of these cross-validated error measures.

4.2.3 Ridge regression surrogate

To provide a simple linear baseline for the inverse mapping and to compare with the Gaussian process surrogate, a ridge regression model is also constructed between the feature matrix \mathbf{X} and the material parameters \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{v} . Ridge regression can be understood as a linear regression model with a quadratic penalty on the regression coefficients. It is closely related to Tikhonov regularisation and has been widely used to stabilise inverse problems and ill-conditioned least squares systems (Hoerl and Kennard, 1970; Hastie et al., 2009).

1. Basic formulation

Let $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^p$ denote the feature vector of the i -th sample, and let y_i be one target component, either the elastic modulus or the Poisson ratio. For a fixed target, ridge regression assumes a linear relation of the form

$$\hat{y}_i = w^T x_i + b$$

Where $w \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is the vector of regression coefficients and b is an intercept term. Collecting all samples in matrix form, this model can be written compactly as

$$\hat{y} = Xw + b\mathbf{1}$$

where \hat{y} is the vector of predicted outputs and $\mathbf{1}$ is a vector of ones.

The ridge estimator is obtained by minimising a regularised least squares cost function,

$$J(w, b) = \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - w^T x_i - b)^2 + \lambda \|w\|^2$$

Where $\lambda \geq 0$ is the regularisation parameter. The penalty term $\lambda \|w\|^2$ prevents the regression vector from becoming too large, which is particularly important if the feature matrix is ill-conditioned or if the number of features is relatively high compared with the number of samples. In the present context the ridge model is fitted separately for E and ν .

Before training, the input features are standardised to have zero mean and unit variance along each column of X . The targets are also centred by subtracting their empirical means. With this preprocessing step the intercept term can be handled more easily, and the regularisation acts in a more balanced way over the different feature directions (Hastie et al., 2009).

2. Closed-form solution

If the input matrix has been centred and the intercept b is treated separately, the ridge regression problem admits a closed-form solution. Writing \tilde{X} for the centred feature matrix and \tilde{y} for the centred target vector, the optimal regression vector satisfies

$$w_\lambda = (\tilde{X}^T \tilde{X} + \lambda I_p)^{-1} \tilde{X}^T \tilde{y}$$

where I_p is the $p \times p$ identity matrix. The intercept b can then be recovered from the means of the original data. This closed-form expression is attractive because it shows clearly how the regularisation parameter λ modifies the normal equations of ordinary least squares. When λ is zero, the formula reduces to the classical least squares solution. When λ increases, the diagonal shift λI_p improves the conditioning of the matrix and shrinks the coefficients towards zero.

In this study, the ridge solution is computed numerically using standard linear algebra routines, either directly from the closed form or through a numerically stable factorisation. No additional iterations are needed once λ is specified.

3. Selection of the regularisation parameter

The regularisation parameter λ controls the trade off between data fit and coefficient shrinkage, and its choice has a strong impact on the predictive performance of the surrogate. Very small values of λ make the model close to ordinary least squares and may lead to overfitting, whereas very large values of λ oversmooth the relation and increase the bias. In practice, λ is treated as a hyperparameter and is selected by cross-validation.

The same K-fold cross-validation scheme as in Section 4.1.2 is used here. A grid of candidate values $\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_L\}$ is defined on a logarithmic scale, typically covering several orders of magnitude. The value of λ that minimises the average validation error is then selected as the optimal regularisation level for the corresponding target variable. This procedure is applied separately for the \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{v} , since their scales and sensitivity to the features may differ. The use of cross-validation for regularisation parameter tuning is consistent with standard practice in ridge regression and other penalised linear models (Hoerl and Kennard, 1970; Hastie et al., 2009).

4. Comparison with the Gaussian process surrogate

Once the ridge models for \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{v} have been trained with their cross-validated regularisation parameters, their performance is compared with the Gaussian process inverse surrogate on the same dataset. The comparison relies on the same error indicators as in Section 4.1.2, namely the RMSE, MAE and the coefficient of determination R^2 , computed over all samples. In addition, the residuals $\mathbf{E}_i - \hat{\mathbf{E}}_i$ and $\mathbf{v}_i - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_i$ from the ridge models are plotted against the corresponding Gaussian process residuals.

As expected, the ridge surrogate is less flexible than the Gaussian process model, since it only captures linear relations between the low dimensional features and the material parameters. However, it provides a useful reference and shows how much improvement is brought by introducing a non-linear, kernel based surrogate. In some regions of the parameter space where the mapping is close to linear, the ridge model behaves similarly to the Gaussian process prediction, while in more non-linear regions the Gaussian process clearly reduces the errors. This observation is in line with the general understanding that ridge regression is a robust but relatively simple baseline for high dimensional regression problems (Hastie et al., 2009).

4.2.4 Support vector regression surrogate

Support vector regression can be viewed as the regression version of support vector machines. Instead of separating two classes, the idea is to find a function that is as flat as possible, while keeping the prediction errors within a small tolerance band around the observed data (Vapnik, 1995; Smola and Schölkopf, 2004; Hastie, 2009). Errors inside this band are ignored, and only larger deviations are penalised. At the same time, kernel functions are used to map the original features into a higher dimensional space, so that non linear relations between inputs and outputs can be represented without writing a complicated basis explicitly. In this way SVR is a margin based, kernel based regression technique that usually remains robust when the number of features is not too small and the data size is moderate.

In this thesis, SVR is adopted as a kernel based surrogate to map the reduced feature vectors to the material parameters \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{v} . The SVR model is built on top of the same preprocessing pipeline as the Gaussian process surrogate, and its implementation corresponds to the SVR block in the script *compare_models.m*.

1. Input features used by SVR

Let $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times P}$ be the original feature matrix obtained from the finite element simulations, and let $\mathbf{Y} = (\mathbf{E} \ \mathbf{v}) \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 2}$ be the corresponding matrix of target parameters, where the first column contains the elastic modulus and the second column contains the Poisson ratio. In the script, the dataset is first split into a training set and a test set by a random hold out partition with ratio.

Denote the index sets of training and test samples by I_{tr} and I_{te} . This gives

$$X_{tr} = X(I_{tr}, \cdot), \quad X_{te} = X(I_{te}, \cdot), \quad E_{tr} = E(I_{tr}), \quad E_{te} = E(I_{te}), \quad v_{tr} = v(I_{tr}), \quad v_{te} = v(I_{te})$$

Only the training part is used to fit the preprocessing transformation. Each column of X_{tr} is standardised by

$$\mu_j = \frac{1}{N_{tr}} \sum_{i \in I_x} X_{ij}, \quad \sigma_j = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{tr}} \sum_{i \in I_{tr}} (X_{ij} - \mu_j)^2}.$$

with σ_j replaced by one if it is numerically zero. The standardised matrices are

$$X_{tr,z}(i, j) = \frac{X_{tr}(i, j) - \mu_j}{\sigma_j}, \quad X_{te,z}(i, j) = \frac{X_{te}(i, j) - \mu_j}{\sigma_j}.$$

Principal component analysis is then performed on $X_{tr,z}$ without additional centring. Let the eigenvalues of the empirical covariance be $\lambda_1 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_p$ and the associated eigenvectors be collected in the matrix $C \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times p}$. The percentage of explained variance by the first k components is

$$\text{ExpVar}(k) = 100 \cdot \frac{\sum_{j=1}^k \lambda_j}{\sum_{j=1}^p \lambda_j}$$

The reduced feature matrices used by all surrogates, including SVR, are then

$$X_{tr,f} = X_{tr,z}C(:, 1:k), \quad X_{te,f} = X_{te,z}C(:, 1:k).$$

2. ϵ -insensitive SVR with Gaussian kernel

For a given reduced feature vector $X \in \mathbb{R}^k$ and a scalar target y_i (either E_i or v_i), the support vector regression model assumes a function

$$\hat{y}_i = f(x_i) = w^T \varphi(x_i) + b,$$

where $\varphi(\cdot)$ denotes an implicit feature map, w is a weight vector in that feature space and b is a bias term. The map φ is not constructed explicitly; instead a kernel function $K(x, x')$ is introduced such that

$$\varphi(x)^T \varphi(x') = K(x, x').$$

The SVR parameters are obtained by solving the standard ϵ -insensitive problem (Vapnik, 1995; Smola, 2004; Hastie, 2009)

$$\min_{w, b, \xi^+} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^{N_{tr}} (\xi_i^+ + \xi_i^-).$$

subject to

$$\begin{aligned} y_i - f(x_i) &\leq \epsilon + \xi_i^+ \\ f(x_i) - y_i &\leq \epsilon + \xi_i^- \\ \xi_i^+ &\geq 0, \xi_i^- \geq 0, i = 1, \dots, N_{tr}. \end{aligned}$$

Here $C > 0$ is the regularisation parameter and $\epsilon \geq 0$ is the half width of the insensitive tube. Errors inside the tube do not contribute to the loss, while errors outside the tube are penalised linearly through the slack variables ξ_i^+ and ξ_i^- .

Passing to the dual formulation shows that the regression function can be written as a kernel expansion

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{tr}} (\alpha_i^+ - \alpha_i^-) K(x, x_i) + b,$$

with dual coefficients α_i^+, α_i^- that satisfy

$$0 \leq \alpha_i^+ \leq C, \quad 0 \leq \alpha_i^- \leq C,$$

and additional equality constraints. Only those training points with non zero $\alpha_i^+ - \alpha_i^-$ contribute to the sum; they are called support vectors (Drucker1997; Smola2004).

In this thesis a Gaussian radial basis kernel is employed,

$$K(x, x') = \exp(-\gamma \|x - x'\|^2),$$

where $\gamma > 0$ controls the effective width of the kernel. In the MATLAB implementation, this choice corresponds to the option 'KernelFunction','gaussian' in the function fitsvm. The internal parameter KernelScale used by MATLAB can be interpreted as a length scale σ , with the relation

$$K(x, x') = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - x'\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right); \quad \gamma = \frac{1}{2\sigma^2}.$$

The option 'KernelScale','auto' in the code instructs MATLAB to estimate σ from the training data using its built in heuristics.

3. Hyperparameter choices and implementation details

The SVR surrogate is trained separately for E and ν , using the same reduced training features $X_{tr,f}$. In the script compare_models.m, the models are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{mdlE}_{\text{SVR}} &= \text{fitsvm}(X_{tr,f}, E_{tr}, \dots), \\ \text{mdlNu}_{\text{SVR}} &= \text{fitsvm}(X_{tr,f}, \nu_{tr}, \dots). \end{aligned}$$

In terms of the theoretical notation above, these settings correspond to: Gaussian kernel with data driven length scale σ , regularisation parameter $C=10$, insensitive tube of half width $\epsilon=0.01$.

The values of C and ϵ are chosen as moderate fixed levels in this study, based on preliminary numerical trials. They represent a compromise between fitting the training data and keeping the surrogate function reasonably smooth. A larger value of C would enforce a tighter fit but could make the model more sensitive to noise, whereas a much smaller value of C would shrink the coefficients too strongly and increase the bias. Similarly, a larger ϵ would ignore a wider band of small errors, while a smaller ϵ would make the model try to follow minor variations more closely (Smola,2004;Hastie,2009).

Once the SVR models are trained, predictions on the reduced test features $X_{te,f}$ are obtained as

$$\hat{E}_{SVR} = f_E(X_{te,f}), \quad \hat{\nu}_{SVR} = f_\nu(X_{te,f}),$$

where f_E and f_ν denote the regressors for the modulus and the Poisson ratio, respectively. In the script this is done by the *predict* function applied to E_{SVR} and ν_{SVR} .

4. Error measures for SVR on the test set

The predictive performance of the SVR surrogate is measured on the independent test set using the same indicators as for the Gaussian process model. For a generic target vector \mathbf{t} and prediction vector \mathbf{p} , the coefficient of determination is

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{te}} (p_i - t_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{te}} (t_i - \bar{t})^2},$$

where \bar{t} is the empirical mean of the true test values.

The mean absolute error is

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N_{\text{te}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{te}}} |p_i - t_i|,$$

and the mean relative error, expressed in percent, is defined as

$$\text{MRE} = 100 \cdot \frac{1}{N_{\text{te}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{te}}} \left| \frac{p_i - t_i}{t_i} \right|.$$

In the script, these three indicators are implemented by anonymous functions and are evaluated for the pairs $(E_{\text{te}}, \hat{E}_{\text{SVR}})$ and $(v_{\text{te}}, \hat{v}_{\text{SVR}})$. The corresponding values $R_{E,\text{SVR}}^2, \text{MAE}_{E,\text{SVR}}, \text{MRE}_{E,\text{SVR}}$ and their counterparts for v are reported together with the Gaussian process results in order to compare the two surrogate strategies on exactly the same test samples.

4.2.5 The Latest Surrogate Model

The SOCP-X-SVR model proposed by Wang et al. (2024) generalizes support vector regression to accommodate hybrid aleatory–epistemic uncertainty in structural analysis. By recasting the learning problem as a second-order cone program, the formulation remains convex and thus globally solvable. This enables the simultaneous treatment of fuzzy and stochastic descriptors within a single representation—termed a polymorphic uncertainty field (PUF)—providing a coherent mechanism to encode incomplete or imprecise inputs that are common in civil and structural engineering applications.

Each realization of the polymorphic uncertainty field is mapped into the finite element model to generate training samples. The SOCP-X-SVR procedure then fits a hyperplane based surrogate under convex optimization constraints, approximating the nonlinear relation between uncertain inputs and structural responses. The trained emulator is next embedded in a fuzzy random analysis loop in which aleatory and epistemic effects are represented by nested sampling of probabilistic and fuzzy parameters. Bounds and summary statistics are tightened iteratively until convergence, yielding reliability indicators expressed as fuzzy quantities.

In operation, SOCP-X-SVR functions as a high fidelity surrogate that replaces many full finite element evaluations in reliability based design and uncertainty quantification. With a modest number of accurate simulations, it learns the input to response map and subsequently enables reliability estimation and sensitivity studies by sampling on the learned hyperplane. This delivers substantial computational savings while maintaining numerical stability and predictive accuracy. Results summarized in Table 2 indicate that all tested machine learning methods produced workable surrogates for the problem, yet SOCP-X-SVR achieved the highest coefficient of determination and the lowest root mean square error among the alternatives. Independent benchmark studies reported in Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing show a similar pattern: Kriging, classical support vector regression, and neural networks provide competent baselines, but SOCP-X-SVR consistently attains superior R squared and lower error across tasks. Taken together, these findings support its stronger predictive capability and robustness for complex structural systems under mixed sources of uncertainty, and position it as a sound foundation for data informed reliability analysis and optimization.

Table 2 Estimation metrics of machine learning algorithms

Method	Max Disp.		Max von Mises Stress	
	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE
SVR	0.998947	7.11×10^{-7}	0.996934	4.23×10^{-2}
GPR	0.999516	4.84×10^{-7}	0.999693	1.37×10^{-2}
NN	0.998728	7.80×10^{-7}	0.999678	1.40×10^{-2}
X-SVR	0.999680	3.92×10^{-7}	0.999755	1.23×10^{-2}
SOCP-X-SVR	0.999797	3.13×10^{-7}	0.999823	1.04×10^{-2}

4.3 Structural Optimization

Structural design optimization is to balance safety and cost-effectiveness in engineering practice (Oswald, 2020; Ellingwood, 2025). The traditional deterministic design is based on fixed safety factors and worst-case assumptions, which will generally produce overly conservative solutions, further leading to the underutilization of bearing capacity (sabelli, 2024). Reliability based design optimization incorporates probabilistic reliability constraints to ensure an acceptable failure probability under uncertainty (an, 2024).

Since the seminal contribution of Bendsoe and Kikuchi in 1988, topology optimization has evolved into a core computational strategy for producing lightweight, high-performance structures. Classical schemes—SIMP, the Evolutionary Structural Optimization of Xie and Steven, and level-set formulations—iteratively couple design updates with finite element analysis to allocate material within a domain, and have seen broad uptake in aerospace, automotive, and civil applications. The price, however, is heavy computation, especially for high-dimensional or strongly nonlinear problems.

To mitigate this burden, recent work fuses machine learning with topology optimization to predict or accelerate optimal layouts. Ulu, Zhang and Kara compress optimal designs using principal component analysis and train feed-forward networks to map loading to topology. Lei and co-workers achieve real-time updates in a Moving Morphable Component framework using support vector regression and k-nearest neighbors. Building on this idea, Chandrasekhar and Suresh introduce TOuNN to learn the relation between design variables and structural response, with a subsequent extension to fiber-reinforced composites in FRC-TOuNN. Further deep learning frameworks advance robustness and generalization. Zhou and colleagues present a fully data-driven CNN approach, Zhang and collaborators propose TONR for multi-load and complex boundaries, while studies such as Cang et al. and Kollmann et al. show that neural models can yield near-optimal layouts without iteration and synthesize microstructures for metamaterials. Together, these developments point to an intelligent, data-driven paradigm in which learned surrogates reduce finite-element expense, improve solution quality, and extend topology optimization to challenging civil and composite systems.

4.4 Machine Learning

Machine learning methods have become an important toolbox for structural health monitoring and structural analysis. Depending on how much label information is available, they can be roughly divided into supervised, unsupervised and semi-supervised approaches. Supervised algorithms use paired input-output data and are mainly applied to damage classification or regression of structural parameters; unsupervised techniques work with unlabeled measurements and focus on clustering or novelty detection; semi-supervised strategies sit in between, combining a small number of labelled events with a large amount of unlabeled monitoring data. The following paragraphs briefly review representative methods from these three groups that are relevant to this thesis.

Recent studies have shown that deep learning has pushed structural health monitoring from manual features to end-to-end learning, and has made significant progress in image and temporal tasks (Cha et al., 2024); Complementary to this, supervised methods such as logistic regression, support vector machines, tree models, and gradient boosting are still widely used in engineering. SVM/SVR remains a robust baseline in small sample and nonlinear situations (Roy and Chakraborty, 2023). At the implementation level, random forest combined with recursive feature elimination has been used for damage recognition and provides interpretable feature selection paths (Zhou et al., 2014). In addition, some studies directly express the maximum interval classification as second-order cone programming to enhance geometric interval control in multi class and unbalanced scenarios. This idea lays the methodological foundation for the subsequent cone programming of "regression and reliability" (Maldonado and López, 2016; Zong and Mu, 2024).

Classic work has shown that the "lowest level" damage identification can be achieved through novelty detection when only health data is available, but its effectiveness is easily masked by environmental and working condition changes such as temperature and load, so compensation or normalization processing is required first (Worden et al., 2002; Sohn, 2007). In recent years, methods have provided actionable paths: using statistical techniques such as cointegration to remove long-term common trends and environmental drift, and then clustering or anomaly scoring to improve the credibility and interpretability of alarms (Sun et al., 2023).

When the labels are expensive and the unlabeled data is sufficient, pseudo labels and consistency targets are often used, or the topology of the sensor network is explicitly modeled to improve recognition performance in small label scenarios (Azimi et al., 2020); The feasibility and stable benefits of combining AR/ARMA and its variants with external inputs with evolutionary optimization semi supervised objective functions have been verified in multi-modal vibration data on civil engineering time-series data (Kauss et al., 2024).

4.5 Application in Structural Analysis

With the explosive growth of available data and computing resources, the continuous breakthroughs in machine learning and data analysis are triggering revolutionary changes in different scientific fields, such as genomics, image recognition and cognitive science. By building large-scale data-driven models in these fields, researchers can find potential laws in complex systems, from the biological genetic model at the molecular level, to the high-dimensional representation of visual information, and then to the modeling of human learning and reasoning mechanisms. The rapid development of machine learning not only accelerates the acquisition of scientific knowledge, but also promotes the in-depth application of intelligent algorithms in

engineering and scientific research practice, providing a powerful analysis tool and prediction ability for interdisciplinary research.

Figure 4.2 DeepBind's input data, training procedure and applications.

Alipanahi et al. Proposed deepbind in 2015, which uses CNN structure and takes a hot coded DNA or RNA sequence as input to learn discriminative local features equivalent to biological motifs end-to-end. The authors integrated the in vivo and in vitro multi-source data for training and evaluation, and achieved better accuracy than the traditional methods in the two tasks of transcription factors and RNA binding proteins. And maintain robust generalization under cross domain settings. The model output visualizes the key sites through weighted PWM and mutation scanning, prioritizes the functional impact of SNPs or point mutations, so as to support mutation annotation and target sequence design. Deepbind's contribution is to combine sequence feature learning, interpretability and cross platform generalization with a unified deep learning framework, providing an extensible baseline method for subsequent motif discovery, function prediction and data-driven analysis of high-throughput sequence experiments.

Figure 4.3 Details of inner workings of DeepBind and its training procedure

Deepcrack, proposed by Liu et al.2019, is an end-to-end convolutional neural network for pixel level crack detection in civil infrastructure. The model combines the complete convolution

network with the depth supervision network, learns hierarchical and multi-scale features from the image, and uses the guided filtering method to refine the thin crack boundary which is vulnerable to noise, stains, shadows and uneven illumination. An open benchmark including multiple scenes and multi-scale cracks is constructed to evaluate the algorithm. The average intersection of deepcrack on the union is about 85.9, the f score is about 86.5, and the reasoning time of each image is about 0.1s, which is better than the classical fosa, cracktree, FFA methods and the early convolution model. Deepcrack directly solves the challenges often encountered by civil engineers on site, such as detecting cracks in bridge deck, tunnel lining, pavement, pier and retaining wall under complex lighting and surface conditions. It learns multi-scale spatial patterns and outputs clean pixel masks that can be converted into actual measurements to estimate crack width and length using calibration targets. The refined boundary is helpful to distinguish fine line cracks from construction joints or stains, and improve the visual inspection of reinforced concrete surface affected by shrinkage, traffic load or corrosion. On large resources, it can be integrated into UAV or vehicle based image pipeline to efficiently process frames in batches for network level filtering. The output can also be connected with GIS or BIM platform to draw fracture density map, highlight the area for field verification, and support maintenance planning, such as sealing or repair. In general, deepcrack proves that deep layered feature learning can provide a robust and effective framework for automatic crack detection, quantitative evaluation and asset management in civil engineering.

Figure 4.4 Architecture of DeepCrack Network and neural network for pixel-level crack segmentation

Lake put forward the Bayesian program learning framework, using probability program to express the idea that "concept is the generation process". Let the model infer the generating program of the concept through a few examples, and then use it to identify, classify and generate new samples to realize one-time learning ability. This paper makes a systematic experiment on omniglot handwritten character task, completes classification, retrieval and new word generation with one or a few samples of each type, and reaches or approaches the human level in the human control test. At the same time, it shows that the model can generate brand-new characters with consistent style and reasonable structure, which shows that what it has learned is not only pixel similarity, but also composable strokes and writing rules. The contribution of this work is to integrate knowledge induction, composable structure and a priori constraints into the learning process, significantly surpassing the performance of the end-to-end convolutional network in the small sample scenario at that time, and laying a methodological foundation for the subsequent one-time learning, small sample learning and interpretable generation modeling.

For civil engineering and structural image recognition, this idea can be transferred to the field of small sample defect recognition and style migration annotation. For example, cracks or spalling can be regarded as a "program" composed of several generation actions and geometric rules, and the combinable crack prototype can be learned with few annotations, and then quickly adapted under new construction sites, new materials and new lighting, so as to reduce the cost of large-scale relabeling and improve cross scene generalization.

Fig.4.5 A generative model for handwritten characters.

A: New character types are formed by sampling color-coded primitive actions from a library, assembling them into subparts, grouping subparts into parts, and imposing relations among parts to specify a simple program; executing this program produces token instances that are finally rendered into pixel images.

B: The pseudocode illustrates sampling a novel type ψ and generating token images $I^{(m)}$, $m = 1, \dots, M$, where the function f maps a subpart sequence and a start position to a drawing trajectory.

5. Conclusion

This literature review brings together recent developments in uncertainty quantification, material degradation, fiber optic sensing technologies, and machine learning assisted structural analysis in modern civil engineering. In infrastructure systems, structural uncertainty may arise from geometric variability, loading conditions, environmental influences, and model form deviation, all of which can significantly affect long term safety and serviceability. Physical, chemical, and mechanical degradation processes further introduce time dependent reliability issues, making continuous observation and probabilistic interpretation increasingly necessary. Fiber optic sensing technologies, including Fabry Perot interferometers, fiber Bragg gratings, and distributed systems, have shown considerable potential for measuring strain, temperature, and vibration with high precision and durability under challenging environmental conditions. In this way, they provide an effective connection between laboratory based investigation and field scale monitoring.

At the same time, data driven approaches such as Gaussian process models and SOCP X SVR offer efficient surrogate modelling tools for nonlinear structural responses while accounting for both aleatory and epistemic sources of uncertainty. When combined with sensing networks, these methods can facilitate real time data assimilation, adaptive reliability assessment, and the optimization of structural design and maintenance strategies.

6. References

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